

CURRENT LAND USE AND THE TREND OF USAGE DURING THE LAST 30 YEARS IN THE DORNEI BASIN, ROMANIA

V. STOILOV-LINU^{1,2}, Ana-Maria DĂNILĂ², B.M. NEGREA^{1,3}

¹Centre of Mountain Economy “CE-MONT” of the National Institute for Economic Research
“Costin C. Kiritescu” – INCE, Romanian Academy, 49 Petreni Street, Vatra Dornei, Romania

²“Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iasi, Geography and Geology Faculty,
Geography Department, 20A Carol I, 700505, Iasi, Romania

³“Ovidius” University of Constanta – Doctoral School of Applied Sciences,
Biology, 58 Ion Voda Street, 900525, Constanta, Romania

E-mail: *linu_valeriu@yahoo.com*

Abstract

The current paradigm towards which modern society tends is that of sustainable development, which has as a starting point the rational use of resources. Land use is thus a crucial element for human society, which imposed the variability of approaches, the inclusion of the statistical component and thus the transposition of qualitative details in quantitative format, in order to quantify the detection of changes in the reference area. The methodology is based on the use of the Corine Land Cover database, processed in order to obtain quantitative data for each category. The main objective of the paper is to highlight the changes in land use in the Dorna basin along with the mapping of use categories, for a period of about 30 years, with related changes. The quantitative results showed major changes in the main categories of use, the most important being found in forests, pastures, cultivated land and in a large part of the artificial areas.

Keywords: *land use, Dorna Basin, changes, CLC, modeling, natural surfaces, anthropic surfaces.*

INTRODUCTION

Land use science can be defined as an inclusive and interdisciplinary subject, as it focuses on materials related to the nature of land use and land cover, their changes in time and space (social, economic, cultural, and political aspects, decision-making), and ecological processes which produce these patterns and changes (Aspinall and Hill, 2007).

The current paradigm towards which modern society tends is that of sustainable development, which has as a starting point the rational use of resources. Land use is shaped by the influence of two broad sets of forces – human needs and environmental characteristics and processes.

The causes, consequences, and control of land use change have become of enormous importance to contemporary society, with the current major concern being the expansion of urban and peri-urban areas and issues related to non-urban land use (Goetz et al., 2005).

Problems with strict reference to the mountainous area, with rural specificity, are based on the intensification of agricultural production or animal husbandry and the existence of abandoned or excluded agricultural lands, the degradation of crop areas by plant intrusions (the emergence of transitional vegetation areas or afforestation on small areas), a minor advantage being obtained by reducing some wetlands and transforming them into agricultural areas or surfaces of interest for carrying out anthropic activities.

From a timeless perspective, the dynamics of detecting land use change is complex, but if we refer to a historical perception, the subject of land use is located at the border between various real controversies and subjective reflections, which can generate overall changes in land use, an example historically being marked by agrarian reforms.

Fig. 1. Study area
Source: authors – 2021

A similar approach was proposed by Doru (2018), which starts from the fact that land use is shaped by two categories of forces, namely human needs and the characteristics of the environmental process, highlighting a spatial and temporal analysis of land use in Iași County, through Corine Land Cover data and satellite imagery. Reinhart et al. (2021), comparatively analyzes the evolution of land use areas in Eastern Europe and the Baltic areas, which were calculated individually to highlight the role of climate on these changes. Büttner (2014) captures the motivation for this data set, the possibilities of use, the history, and importance of CORINE Land Cover (CLC), a project that was created to standardize the collection of land data in Europe and to support the development of environmental policy an approach that includes examples of evolution.

The aims of the paper are to establish the areas for which the changes are significant, in a quantitative manner, and the graphical and cartographic representation of the use of the land for a temporary period 1990–2018. The main objective of the paper is to highlight the changes in land use in the Dorna Basin along with the mapping of use categories, for a period of about 30 years, with related changes. Along with this, the definition of quantifiable values for each category in the CLC is the basis for determining the qualitative characteristics for the Dorna Basin.

The Dorna Basin is located in the northwest of the Bistrița River Basin, is located entirely in the mountainous area (Figure 1), at the border between the Northern Group and the Central Group of the Eastern Carpathians. The altitudinal gap is between 800 m in the depression area (Dorna Depression) and the valley corridors where the altitudes increase radially and reach 1900 m, in the Călimani Mountains (south of the basin). The north of the Dorna Basin is represented by the Bârgău Mountains and the Suhard Mountains, with more significant altitudes in the northern and north-western areas. The hydrographic network is marked by the presence of rivers such as: Dorna, Dornișoara, Teșna, Neagra or Coșna.

From a climatic point of view, we can refer to an average annual temperature of 5.2–6°C, in July the average temperature is 14–15°C, and 5–6°C in January. Precipitation has average values between 800–850 mm/year, and the dominant wind direction is southwest. It is worth mentioning the duration of days with snow, these exceeding on average the value of 120 days per year, according to the data provided by www.meteomanz.com, for the Poiana Stampei station, located in the central area of the Dorna Basin.

METHODOLOGY

Land is a concept that refers to the physical environment that includes specific components such as relief and geomorphological characteristics, the soil layer, the hydrographic network, plant forms, and the general climatic context, with local influences. How they impose themselves on the potential of land use contributes to the formation of particularities on a case-by-case basis.

At the same time, the anthropic factor is included, with the resulting aspects, respectively constructions, industrial areas, mining areas and tailings dumps, leisure spaces, infrastructure network, or dump sites. Purely economic and social characteristics are not included in the concept of land; they are part of the economic and social context (FAO, 1976).

Land cover is the biophysical state of the Earth's surface and the immediate subsurface (Douglas et al., 1994). In other words, the land cover describes the physical condition of the

land surface that can be described: in cultivated areas, mountains, or forests (Meyer, 1994). Land use involves both how the biophysical attributes of land are manipulated and the intent behind the purpose for which the land is used (Douglas et al., 1994).

Finally, FAO (1995) argues that land use refers to the function or purpose for which land is used by the local population and can be defined as the totality of human activities that are directly related to land, use its resources, or which have an impact on them.

From this perspective, land use and land cover are differentiated concepts, which cannot be treated under equivalent aspects, although sometimes they tend to overlap, the need for distinction being emphasized in environmental impact analyses, through the manifested changes.

In the analysis of land use and land cover change, it is first necessary to conceptualize the meaning of "change". At an elementary level, land use and land cover by quantitative means, change depending on the size of the area (increase or decrease) of a certain type of land use or land cover (Briassoulis, 2000).

Changes in land use include two different elements: changes in land cover, an exchange from one type of cover to another, such as the conversion of forests to agricultural land, and changes in the intensity of land use and the way a certain type of coverage is used (Lambin and Helmut, 2006).

The methodological aspects of obtaining cartographic materials are the use of the classification system proposed in the Corine Land Cover (CLC) project. Thus, the land use classes are built according to the classical methodology and keep the theme of the project inventory (CLC 2006 Technical Guidelines). The software used to complete the mapping materials is ArcMap 10.8, a component of the ArcGIS program provided by ESRI. Sixteen land use classes were selected (Table 1), described according to the Corine Land Cover legend, for a total area of 602.92 km². The land use maps were made for 5 different periods: 1990, 2002, 2006, 2012, 2018.

Practical applicability starts from the concept of modeling. Thus, the determination of anthropogenic pressure from a quantitative perspective is important in order to establish natural resources and their relationship with human needs, and when field validation takes place for reference areas, the methodology can be applied to pilot areas in mountain areas of Romania.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Detection of changes in the GIS environment is a process that helps to measure the intensity of changes between two or more time intervals (Alvarez and Olmedo, 2017). It most often involves the comparison between two satellite images or between two aerial photographs with different acquisition data, covering the same area of interest (Lu et al., 2003).

Detection of changes in the complex variant involves the analysis of several classes over two-time intervals. The basic principles are the same, but it increases the complexity of the analysis. Change detection studies should provide the following information (Lu et al., 2003): change in area and rate of change; spatial distribution of modified classes; the trajectory of changes in land use classes and the assessment of the accuracy of the results of change detection.

The CLC maps made for the 5 different periods (Figure 2) use a minimum mapping unit (MMU) of 25 hectares (ha) for the extensive surface phenomena and a minimum width of 100 m for the linear phenomena.

The differences for the main categories of land use were significant in the time gap 1990–2018 (Table 1).

Table 1. The actual values of land use areas in the Dorna Basin and the legend according to Corine Land Cover

Land use code	Surface (sq km) 1990	Surface (sq km) 2000	Surface (sq km) 2006	Surface (sq km) 2012	Surface (sq km) 2018	Land use legend
112	9.17	9.17	11.04	11.23	11.23	Discontinuous urban fabric
131	0.95	0.95	0.94	1.22	1.22	Mineral extraction sites
132	0.00	0.00	0.59	0.59	0.59	Dump sites
142	0.38	0.38	0.00	0.00	0.00	Sport and leisure facilities
211	0.00	0.00	24.79	14.63	14.63	Non-irrigated arable land
231	71.71	73.08	56.54	63.44	63.43	Pastures
242	28.39	28.37	23.98	29.70	29.70	Complex cultivation patterns
243	50.58	49.02	8.24	8.07	8.07	Land principally occupied by agriculture, with significant areas of natural vegetation
311	0.00	0.00	6.58	4.93	4.13	Broad-leaved forest
312	371.58	372.49	382.75	353.51	340.71	Coniferous forest
313	20.58	22.04	35.81	28.49	27.89	Mixed forest
321	1.71	1.71	28.09	30.30	30.71	Natural grasslands
322	10.17	10.16	5.68	5.64	5.58	Moors and heathland
324	37.68	35.51	17.87	51.15	65.01	Transitional woodland-shrub
333	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	Sparsely vegetated areas
511	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	Water courses
TOTAL	602.92	602.92	602.92	602.92	602.92	

The category of *discontinuous urban space and rural space* registered an increase in area, 0.34%, mainly due to the expansion of built-up areas and recently developed commercial units. The *mineral extraction sites* stagnated at 1.22 km² in 2018, with an insignificant increase, compared to previous years. The area covered by *dump sites* reaches 0.59 km², a value that has been maintained since 2006, a class not found in the past. *Sport and leisure facilities* have values below 25 ha after 2000 and are thus not included in the reference values of the more recent CLC polygons.

Fig. 2. Land use in Dorna Basin (1990–2018). Source: CLC, EEA
Source: authors 2021

The complex of *non-irrigated arable land* has had a high extension since 2006, respectively 24.79 km², with decreasing tendencies of up to 1.68%. The *pastures* had an oscillating evolution, reaching from an initial area of 71.71 km² in 1990 to 56.54 km² in 2006, a significant decrease, corroborated with reduction of the potential of the zootechnical productions, by reducing the quantity of food and implicitly of the quality of the fodder. This trend is also maintained for *complex crops*, which have decreased in value by up to 6 km², often the areas being agglutinated to other classes or transformed into arable land. *Land principally occupied by agriculture, with significant areas of natural vegetation* has suffered important decreases, compared to their total share, while *broad-leaved forests* have areas of less than 1% of the total.

Coniferous forests have supremacy, the weight of forest area reaches a maximum of 382.75 km² (63.48%) in 2006, with percentage decreases of up to 5.21% (2012) and 2.12% (2018), a cause important being the exploitation of wood and the development of some transition categories. *Mixed forests* show the same trends, but on much smaller areas, reaching a maximum of 35.81 km². One thing to note is the continuous increase of the *natural grassland* areas 4.81%, an important element because the grasslands have a multifunctional character, and the function better known and easy to use in the local consciousness is the production, in the mountain area and promotes animal husbandry by harvesting and transforming plant elements into fodder.

Moors and heathland have halved in recent times, in 2018 their area is 5.58 km². For the *transitional woodland-shrub* category, the area fluctuates considerably for a long time, the individual evolution chart has a concave shape, with growth trends towards 2018, with an area of 65.01 km², being an extended category within the Dorna Basin, but also an important argument in the appearance of general changes at the forestry level. *Sparingly vegetated areas* and *water courses* have very small areas, less than 0.02% of the total.

Fig. 3. The weights calculated for land use areas in Dorna Basin

Data source: CLC, EEA

Overall, the weight of land use classes out of the total of 602.92 km², presents different values for the 5 periods, the most significant changes in the period 1990–2018, where the oscillations are significant, these being valid for coniferous forests, mixed forests, transition areas (forest-bush), pastures, and anthropic space. (Figure 3).

Human society is currently facing various challenges, including resource constraints due to ever-increasing demand, degradation of productive land, reduced biodiversity, and climate change with serious repercussions on all human activities but also on the environment. Thus, this issue indicates the need for rational use of resources and at the level of the basin analyzed, the next step is to design a method for determining the optimal use of land, based on a conceptual framework for establishing use policies to support, improve productivity and maintain the resilience of the ecosystem to various changes.

Land use planning is part of an integrated resource management mechanism, which begins with an assessment of the land resource base (land assessment), identification of needs and challenges followed by the selection and implementation of the optimal approach by implementing decision support systems ranging from the farm to the regional or national landscape (Feranec et al., 2017).

CONCLUSIONS

This study aims to analyze the temporal and spatial changes of the main categories of land use and land cover by using the CORINE Land Cover (CLC) database, identifying and analyzing the areas where evolution is felt and at the same time the rendering of perspectives on land use change/coverage.

For the mountainous area, forest areas (broad-leaved, coniferous), mixed forests (mixed), pastures, meadows, and non-irrigated arable land predominate. They have an increased share, given that the accessibility and the possibility of expanding crops in the area are restrictive characteristics or very difficult to manage in order to obtain new agricultural areas. Significant spatial changes related to land use dynamics took place in the 1990s (transition period) and took place after 2000. One of the major changes during the transition period was the expansion of private ownership of agricultural and forestry land to collective ownership, which was characteristic of the previous period. The tools and methodology used in land resource planning must support their users to manage them efficiently and increase productivity. In this way, sustainable agriculture is supported, along with food systems, by promoting improved governance of land resources to meet the needs of society (Jones and Clark, 1997).

Modeling land-use trends in the Dornei Basin can be representative of mountainous areas in Romania. This analysis is based on the rational management of natural areas, compared to anthropic, simultaneously reflecting the specific development of mountain communities and the forecast of evolution.

The main problem posed by the use of the CLC database is the validation of results by field actions, which can be limited in time and space, point validation zones need to be taken from known areas, accessible, and with the possibility of evaluation during studies. Steps are needed towards a new spatial organization and whether it is in line with a long-term policy of sustainable development in mountain areas.

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